

Profile of Cancer Patients who Sought Alternative Care of Siddha at the Ayothidaspandithar Hospital, National Institute of Siddha, 2017-2022

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Abstract:

Background

Cancer is the second most common cause of death and one of the most difficult non-communicable diseases to treat. The Tamil Nadu Cancer Registry Project has shown that for Tamil Nadu's population of 80 million, the crude incidence rate (CIR) of all cancers per 1,00,000 population was 93.9 for women and 74.4 for men, with the highest CIR in Chennai (140.8). The Siddha medical system can treat all ailments, and research has proven that Siddha drugs can effectively treat cancer.

Objective

This study explored the characteristics of cancer patients who sought alternative treatment of Siddha at Ayothidas Pandithar Hospital (APH) at the National Institute of Siddha from 2017 to 2022.

Methods

The patient data was collected retrospectively from the hospital-based cancer registry at the special OPD of APH from January 2017 to December 2022. The diagnosis of the cases and treatment were taken as reported and documented in the patient record. MS Office was used for data entry and creating charts. Descriptive statistics were calculated using SPSS software for Windows (version 21.0, Chicago, IL, USA), and the map was drawn using ArcGIS version 10 software (ESRI, Redlands, CA, USA)

Results

A total of 1131 cancer patients attended the Siddha Special OPD at APH. Significantly more men (55.4%) opted for alternative Siddha therapy. A higher percentage of patients (31%) belonged to the 60 to 69 year age group. Based on the stromal histological features, 82% were found to be malignant. The two most prevalent cancers were gastrointestinal Cancer (45%) and gynecological Cancer (21%). Also, the most common tumors sought alternative treatment were

gastrointestinal cancers in males (44%) and gynecological cancers (49%) in women. Siddha regimen was more than one-third (36%) of the patients' first course of treatment, and 17% received more than one therapy. Five percent of the patients were diagnosed and treated on the same day, with the alternative Siddha treatment, while 29% were within a month. Most of the patients (95%) were from Tamil Nadu, and their geographical distribution was dispersed all over the state.

Conclusion

The study examined the characteristics and treatment-seeking behavior of APH cancer patients seeking alternative therapies. The study's findings suggest that further investigation is necessary to comprehend the outcome of Siddha cancer treatment and to propagate that Siddha cancer therapy is safe and helpful.

Keywords – Cancer care, Siddha treatment, Cancer registry, Patient profile

Introduction:

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are a significant public health concern. And 60% of deaths in India are attributed to non-communicable diseases. The four common NCDs responsible for the escalated mortality rates are Cardiovascular diseases, Chronic respiratory diseases, Cancer, and Diabetes.[1] Cancer is the second leading cause of death and the most challenging non-communicable disease worldwide. The global burden of Cancer, as reflected in the Globoscan 2018, is about 18.1 million new cases and 9.6 million deaths.[2] The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) projected 16.3 million deaths from Cancer and 29.5 million new cases by 2040.[3] Global Burden of Disease in India in 2016 reports that Cancer accounted for 5.7% of all fatalities and cancer mortality can increase to 0.70 million by the year 2026 as a result of changes in the size and composition of the population.[4],[5]

The Tamil Nadu Cancer Registry Project statistics (2016) showed that the Crude Incidence Rate (CIR) of all cancers per 1,00,000 population was 93.9 among women and 74.4 among males, with the highest CIR in Chennai (140.8).[6] The World Health Organisation encourages the use of traditional medicines in the healthcare system, citing their affordable cost and accessibility.[7] National healthcare policies emphasize using an integrated medical system that promotes illness prevention and management.[9] The Ayothidos Pandithar Siddha Hospital (APH), campus-based at the National Institute of Siddha, offers dynamic healthcare services to the public and clinical training to undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral students. The hospital conducts special OPDs for Cardiac ailments, non-communicable diseases, Cancer, Obesity, Diabetes, Geriatrics, and Infertility. The Cancer Special OPD is undertaken every Wednesday between 8 a.m. and 12 noon.

Objective

This study explores the characteristics of cancer patients who sought Siddha treatment at Ayothidas Pandithar Siddha Hospital (APH), attached to the National Institute of Siddha, from 2017 to 2022.

Subjects and Methods:

Study Setting and Population

The patient data was extracted retrospectively from the hospital-based cancer registry of special OPD at APH from January 2017 to December 2022.

Study Variables and Study Tools

The variables considered for the analysis were gender, age, number of patients who sought treatment year-wise, district-wise, primary tumour site, tumour behaviour, and nature of the treatment. The diagnosis of the cases and treatment were taken as reported and documented in the patient record. MS Office was used for data entry and creating charts. Descriptive statistics were calculated using SPSS software for Windows (version 21.0, Chicago, IL, USA), and the map was drawn using ArcGIS version 10 software (ESRI, Redlands, CA, USA)

Data analysis

A descriptive analysis was carried out, and the results were presented in the form of frequencies and proportions. The geographical distribution of the patients seeking treatment was shown as a Choropleth map.

Ethical approval

The study is a secondary data analysis using available hospital cancer registry records. Hence, administrative approval was sought from the Director of the National Institute of Siddha, Chennai.

Results:

About 1131 cancer patients were treated during the study period from January 2017 to December 2022. (Figure 1). On average, 189 patients sought alternative Siddha treatment in a year at APH. In 2020 and 2021, there was a decrease in number of patients during the COVID-19 pandemic situation. Among those who sought treatment at APH (Figure 2), 55% were males, and 45% were females, which was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). The patient's age ranged from 2 to 93 years. The age group 60 to 69 years had the highest frequency, followed by 50 to 59 years. Only four of the children were under the age of ten. Thirty-nine percent of all patients were between the ages of 60 and 80 (Figure 3).

Figure 1

Distribution of cancer patients who sought treatment at APH during 2017-2022.

Figure 2
Gender wise distribution of cancer patients

Figure 3
Age and gender-wise distribution of Cancer patients who sought treatment at APH 2017-2022

Patients came from various places (Figure 4), with the majority being from Tamil Nadu (95.4%) and 1.9% hailing from other states. Patients outside Tamil Nadu (n=24) were from Andaman and Nicobar Islands (n=1), Andhra Pradesh (n=10), Karnataka (n=5), Kerala (n=1), New Delhi (n=2), Pondicherry (n=2), Telangana (n=2), and West Bengal (n=1) were among them. The geographical distribution of patients within Tamil Nadu is shown in (Figure 5).

Figure 4
 Distribution of patients treated at APH between 2017 and 2022 by place of residence

Figure 5
 The distribution of patients treated at APH by the residential district between 2017 and 2022.

Patients were widely dispersed in all states, whereas the north eastern region of Tamil Nadu, Chennai, and its surrounding districts had more patients, which might be attributed to the hospital's proximity.

The GIT (gastrointestinal tract) was the site of Cancer in 45% of the patients, followed by gynecological cancer (22.3%), which includes breast and cervical cancer, and subsequently respiratory tract cancer (9.7%). Skin and cancers of the brain and spinal cord were fewer in number (Figure 6). Only 12.8% of cancer cases were in situ, while 81.1% had malignant behavior (Table 1).

Figure 6

Percentage distribution of different cancers treated at APH 2017-2022

GIT – Gastrointestinal tract cancer includes the esophagus, stomach, intestine, colon, rectum, etc. Excretory – kidney and urinary bladder cancers. ; Head & Neck – cancers of ears, nose, pharynx, oral cavity, parotid glands, thyroid, etc.; Gynaecological – breast cancers, ovaries, uterus, cervix, and vagina; Haematology – Leukemia, lymphomas, and lymph nodes; Male genitalia – prostate, Penile, and testicular cancers; Respiratory – larynx, trachea, bronchus, and lung cancers; Musculoskeletal – cancers of the bone and sarcomas; Non-specific– cases of unidentified primary sites.

Figure 7

Gender-wise distribution of various cancers.

Table 1

Behaviour of the cancer patient at APH, 2017-2022

Behaviour	Frequency	Percent
Borderline	59	5.1
In SITU	145	12.8
Malignant	927	81.9

Over one-third of the patients' initial therapy (36%) was Siddha, and 1.1% had taken AYUSH treatment. Nearly 49% of the population seeks Siddha treatment after modern treatment. It may be due to prolonging their survival, avoiding relapses, and improving their QOL. Fourteen percent of patients were unaware of their first treatment (Table2).

Table 2

Treatments already taken before Siddha treatment at APH, 2017-2022

Treatment taken	Frequency	Percent
No treatment was taken (First therapy, Siddha)	409	36.2
AYUSH treatment taken earlier	12	1.1
Modern treatment		
Chemotherapy alone	156	13.8
Surgery alone	143	12.6
Chemotherapy and Radiotherapy	82	7.3
Radiotherapy alone	51	4.5
Surgery, Chemotherapy, and Radiotherapy	49	4.3
Surgery and Chemotherapy	43	3.8
Surgery and Radiotherapy	16	1.4
Allopathy oral medication	12	1.1
Total	552	48.8
Not known	158	14.1

On the day the diagnosis was confirmed, 5% of patients contacted Siddha treatment options; 29% did so within a month, and 57.7% did so within six months. The frequency distribution shows people are seeking alternative options and reflects the need for complementary therapies in cancer treatment (Table 3).

Table 3

The duration between diagnosis and treatment at APH, Cancer care patients, 2017-2022

The duration between APH treatment and diagnosis	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Same day	59	5.2	5.2
2 nd day - < 1 month	272	24.0	29.2
1 - <6 months	322	28.5	57.7
6 months -< 1 year	119	10.5	68.2

1 - < 2 years	104	9.2	77.4
2 - < 3 years	38	3.4	80.8
3 - < 4years	30	2.7	83.5
4 - <5years	28	2.5	86.0
5+years	50	4.4	90.4
Not known	109	9.6	100.0
Total	1131	100	100.0

Discussion:

The current study analyzed the cancer patients who attended the Siddha Cancer Special OPD of Ayothidas Pandithar Hospital at Tambaram Sanatorium during 2017-2022. Around 1131 cancer patients attended the Siddha cancer care special OPD at APH. Significantly more men (55.3%) sought treatment at APH during the study period. According to a Tamil Nadu Cancer Registry Project (TNCRP-2016) report jointly produced by the state health department and the Cancer Institute, more women than males are battling Cancer [6]. However, our study frequency reflects that seeking alternative treatment in cancer care was higher among men than women. The age group ranged from 2 to 93 years. Nearly thirty-one percent of the patients were in the age group 60- 69 years, followed by 50- 59 years (25%) and 40-49 years (16%). In the present study, the most prevalent cancer was gastrointestinal Cancer (45%), also found to be predominant among men. In a retrospective study of gastrointestinal cancers in a tertiary care hospital [11], the maximum incidence of cancers (55.1%) was recorded in the age group between 40 and 60. The incidence of gastrointestinal cancers was significantly higher in the men (65.8%) than the women (34.1%). It agrees with the findings of our study.

TNCRP report states the five leading sites of Cancer in Tamil Nadu in men were the stomach (8.9%), mouth (8.3%), lung(8%), tongue (5.6%), oesophagus (4.7%), and in women, it was breast (26.3%), cervix (20.6%), ovary (5.3%), mouth (3.7%) and stomach (3.5%). According to WHO, Lung, prostate, colorectal, stomach, and liver cancer are the most common types of Cancer in men, while breast, colorectal, lung, cervical, and thyroid cancer are the most common among women [10]. The predominant among women cases seeking the Siddha regimen at APH was Gynaecological cancer (47.4%), like breast and cervical cancer, whereas among men, it was gastrointestinal tract cancer (56.4%).

In various hospital-based studies conducted across the country, Aggarwal et al [11]. from Punjab, Conjeevaram et al [12]. from Andhra Pradesh, Ashat et al [13]. from Chandigarh, and Bengal et al [14]. from Maharashtra, similar observations were made, with all of them reporting the largest incidence of Cancer in the age group of 40–69 years. The distribution of the population's demographics, like the predominant age group (50-69) years of cancer cases, aids in identifying illness risk factors and developing early intervention strategies.

In 81 percent of patients, the Cancer's behaviour was malignant, and only 12.8 percent was in situ. Patients originated from various locations, spread across all directions over Tamil Nadu, and were not confined to one particular district. Even patients outside Tamil Nadu had traveled a long way and sought treatment at APH, showing their thirst for the alternative regimen. The northeast region showed a higher number of cases, possibly due to the hospital location's proximity. In 81 percent of patients, the Cancer's behaviour was malignant, and only 12.8 percent was in situ.

Five percent of patients sought Siddha treatment options on the same day immediately after confirming the diagnosis; another 24 percent did so within a month, and another 28.5 percent did so within six months. Ultimately, most (57.5) of the patients had sought an alternative treatment of Siddha within a short time of diagnosis of six months.

Nearly 49% of the patients who had modern treatment have also sought the alternate treatment of Siddha. Their vocabulary version of the approach to Siddha treatment was to improve their quality of life and increase their life span.

Siddha medicines have been used in cancer care for centuries. Siddha medicines help people fight the disease and boost their immunity [15]. Quality of life is a crucial concern in cancer patients. The multitude of symptoms experienced affect their general, physical, psychological, and economic well-being and their familial relationships with fear of relapse, fatigue, presence of pain, sleep issues, difficulty in supporting their families, and economic decline post-treatment [16]. An integrative medical practice requires a good understanding of different medical systems and well-defined treatment protocols for specific diseases and their stages. Practitioners of one system of medicine may be trained in the other system, or there can be a collaboration between practitioners of different medical systems. In integrative medical practice, the focus is on addressing the unmet needs of the patient and ensuring the best clinical outcome in the given R. Puthiyedath et al[17]., 2023

Patients who are physically unfit for surgery, chemo-radiation therapy in terms of age, health status, relapse of symptoms after surgery and chemo-radiation treatments, and with chemo-radiation severe adverse effects, unable to tolerate and continue further cycles of treatment encounter Siddha cancer care treatments. According to an earlier study, increased drug resistance and soaring side effects of chemotherapy and radiotherapy make people look for alternative treatment options [18]. Based on the experience with patients, Dr CP Mathew clarifies that in some cases, the addition of Siddha and Ayurveda medicines helps better tolerate chemotherapy and improves clinical outcomes. In other patients, he says that, to his surprise, the growth of the tumor could be arrested, and at times, total remission has been achieved. R. Puthiyedath et al[17]., 2023

Several studies have demonstrated that the Siddha regimen helps treat breast cancer and effectively manages chemo-radiation therapy's adverse effects [19]. In Siddha medicine, there have been several instances of treating cancer patients successfully. Integrative approaches are gaining momentum globally in the field of Cancer. J.J. Mao et al[20]., 2021 Integrative Oncology is an emerging discipline in the West but is yet to strike roots in India. This study shows an overview of the characteristics of the cancer patients seeking alternative treatment of Siddha at APH. Further in-depth studies to explore the reasons for seeking treatment in Siddha and various treatments given in the hospital to manage different cancers will help develop an integrated treatment approach for effective management of Cancer.

Limitations

The results pertain to the cancer patients seeking Siddha Special OPD at APH during the study period and may not represent the entire malignant population.

Conclusion

On average, 189 patients were treated per year during the study period. Gastrointestinal cancer was the predominant site of Cancer in men, whereas in women, it was breast and cervical cancer. Siddha was more than one-third of the patients' initial therapy. It demonstrates the patients' faith in alternative treatment. Nearly 58% of patients sought Siddha treatment within six months of diagnosis, and 5% sought the APH Special OPD on the same day. The characteristics and treatment-seeking behaviours of cancer patients at APH are outlined in this research. However, an in-depth study is required to comprehend the Siddha cancer treatment's outcome and propagate that Siddha cancer therapy is safe and helpful.

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